
CSCCE Glossary: Virtual events

Introduction

With the onset of the global COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020 came a largescale shift to depending on virtual events for community building. Many community managers found themselves by necessity trying new tools and tactics to host successful virtual events, and so in May of 2022 [we convened a community call](#) to coalesce this knowledge into a new resource: this glossary section on virtual events.

The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE)'s community management glossary is a growing resource with several themed sections focusing on specific topics. You can find all of the terms to date in our [online glossary](#) on the CSCCE website, where additional terms are added over time.

Similar to the [Inclusive Language in Community Building](#) section of the glossary, this section is conceptualized as an “active glossary,” where we try to provide context for how, where, and why you as a community manager might come across these terms rather than just offering definitions. One way of looking at this resource is as a collection of discussion prompts: If you work with others, try taking a few relevant terms and descriptions to your next staff meeting or coffee hour and see where the conversation takes you.

We welcome feedback on the terms included as well as suggestions of additions and encourage you to [join the conversations](#) in our community of practice.

About CSCCE

The Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE) champions the importance of human infrastructure for effective collaboration in STEM. We provide training and support for the people who make scientific collaborations succeed at scale and we also research the impact of these emerging roles.

Find out more about us on our website: cscce.org

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ACCESSIBILITY

The concept of whether a product, service, or space can be used by as broad an audience as possible, which differs from general usability by focusing on providing an equivalent user experience to people with disabilities. Factors that make up accessibility include visual, auditory, and mobility components, and the ability of a product, service, or space to interface or be used with assistive technology (such as a screen reader or mobility aids).

Specifically, when thinking about virtual environments, accessibility considerations include providing closed captioning and/or subtitles, ensuring the platforms you use are screen reader compatible, offering asynchronous content, and ensuring participants have multiple ways that they can take part (e.g., text-based messaging and opportunities to connect one-on-one or in small groups).

Further reading: [Ensuring Virtual Events are Accessible for All](#), by RespectAbility: Lauren Appelbaum and Eric Ascher

ACCESSIBILITY STATEMENT / GUIDELINES

A statement developed by the host and/or planning committee to highlight their commitment to making the event accessible and explain how they plan to achieve this goal.

Example: [RSECon2022's accessibility statement](#)

AGENDA DESIGNER

The person or people responsible for designing the event, including defining overall goals and shaping content that meets the goals. This may be, but does not have to be, the same person or people who fill the role of Moderator.

ARCHIVING OF ARTIFACTS

Virtual events often create digital artifacts such as shared documents or brainstorming boards. Your archiving process will consider the purpose of these artifacts; whether you need to change access permissions after an event and, if so, how soon; whether artifacts are to remain public and for how long; how the artifacts can be found (e.g., on a shared resources page); and whether there are additional editing or formatting steps that you as curator need to undertake. The intended use and audience(s) for artifacts should be made clear upfront to those contributing, and authorship should be appropriately acknowledged.

ASYNCHRONOUS CONTENT

Event-related participation that can be done on an attendee’s own schedule; does not require “live” participation. Digital examples include pre- or post-event recordings of presentations, discussion boards where topics are posed and answered, and messaging tools that allow attendees to interact outside of sessions. Face to face equivalents might include posters (that are left up outside of poster sessions), an expo fair with information to pick up, and other exhibits to peruse outside of live sessions.

Offering digital asynchronous content makes an event more inclusive by allowing participants to interact with content in their own time zone, when they have access to childcare, or using modes of communication that they prefer (e.g., written rather than spoken communications).

See also: Synchronous content

BACKCHANNEL

From the perspective of virtual event participants, a backchannel is a (most often) public space for communication and annotation of the conversation, resource sharing, and a way of communicating without needing a working microphone or quiet space. Examples include Zoom Chat, Slack, and Twitter (using an event hashtag).

From the perspective of the event organizers, a backchannel is a private communication channel via which they can communicate about technical problems, scheduling changes, and other time-sensitive issues.

CAMERA ETIQUETTE

A set of norms around what is appropriate, and not appropriate, as it relates to the livestreaming (or pre-recorded) video of participants, speakers, organizers, etc. Examples include having your camera on for a stated portion of the event, or subevent types and having good lighting and clear audio when you’re a presenter.

Different events serve different purposes, so keep this in mind when you set norms around whether you expect participants to turn on their cameras or not. Having cameras turned off allows participants to take a break from seeing themselves ([known to be unsettling](#)) and/or things needing their attention in their surroundings (bio breaks, child care, an unexpected visitor, or meal times).

CAPTIONS

Captions appear on screen in real-time and include non-speech sounds, not just spoken audio, to improve the accessibility of your event including for those who are deaf, hard of hearing, or are not native speakers of the language being used. Closed captioning means text can be turned on/off by the listener. Groups considering using an AI-based captioning service should carefully read the

platform's privacy policy first as many tools record events in order to improve their algorithms. There are additional human transcription services for live captioning that may be more secure and also improve the accuracy of captions for specialized topics.

See also: Subtitles

CODE OF CONDUCT COMMITTEE / RESPONDERS

A group that processes and responds to reports of code of conduct violations during an event. This group may or may not also be involved in creating the code of conduct or community participation guidelines.

CURATION AND CONTENT MANAGEMENT

Virtual events can often produce a lot of content, e.g., virtual notes, whiteboards, recordings. As a convenor, you should think upfront about your content management practices, how to convey those practices to participants, and how to support them in being part of the content management process. This might include using release forms and adding relevant information to your speaker guide as well as asking for paid or volunteer curators, note-takers, live-scribes and post-event reporters to help with creating, editing, summarizing and sharing event artifacts.

See also: Archiving of artifacts

DISCORD

This is a platform that was initially adopted by the gaming community. During the pandemic, many communities started using this platform as it offers both text and audio communications as well as the ability to screenshare. Discord also provides an easy way for participants to “switch” between channels and view their version of “breakout” rooms.

DRY RUN / DRESS REHEARSAL

A rehearsal of all key technical transitions of the event before the live event. This often involves the moderator/host, facilitators, and technical support, but also instructors/presenters who would like to practice using your event platform ahead of time in order to feel comfortable presenting their content.

DUTIES ROSTER

A list of event roles and responsibilities and who will do them. The goal here is to ensure that everyone knows what is expected of them, as well as be able to easily contact a relevant person/team. This may be public or private to the event team. Don't forget to circulate the roster to the relevant people ahead of the event and ideally host it in a central, shared space that can be referred to.

EVENT PRODUCER

This person's role is to take on any tasks related to technically running an event so that the speaker or facilitator/moderator is free to focus on content and conversation. They assist with tasks such as creating and managing breakout rooms and monitoring the chat, as well as ensuring links to relevant content are shared and accessible to participants (e.g., a virtual notes doc).

See also: Technical facilitator

FACILITATOR

An individual who is running a stand-alone event such as a workshop, or a session within a larger event. A facilitator aims to engage the participants in a way that is inclusive and supports the group in working together responsively to address the event's topics. Facilitators may be members of the community, part of the event organizing team or staff, or they may be external professionals engaged to guide a group towards a defined goal.

See also: Moderator, Technical facilitator, Event producer

GITHUB REPO

A Github repository is a collaborative virtual platform that allows for sharing, tracking, and versioning of various resources, particularly code. There are many features that can be leveraged, including a way to track progress through "issues" (a bit like a ticketing system). For communities that are already in the habit of using it, Github may be a very good option to use alongside your virtual event. A hackathon is an example of an event that would likely leverage Github or a similar tool.

Example: [Data Umbrella sprints repo](#)

HASHTAG

A short, set phrase used with a “#” in front of it on certain social media platforms, which is used so attendees can easily search for conversations about the event on social media and others can follow along with what is happening at the event. The event hashtag is often set by the event organizers and publicized to all event attendees and “followers” on platforms. Where possible, it's helpful to include it prominently in the event agenda and other event information materials.

To make your hashtag accessible to screen readers, ensure that each word is capitalized (e.g., #TheCSCCEVirtualEventHashtag).

HYBRID EVENT

An event at which some attendees and/or presenters are participating in-person and some attendees and/or presenters are participating virtually. This might involve all in-person participants gathering at the same place or a series of local event “hubs” happening within a certain timeframe. Participants

may have access to asynchronous content in order to facilitate connections across time zones.

See also: Asynchronous content, Synchronous content

ICEBREAKER

An activity designed to facilitate the formation of connections between participants in an event who likely do not know one another. There are many different formats for both virtual and in-person icebreakers that range from roundtable introductions to intricate games and activities. Remember that participants may have different comfort levels with icebreaker activities and be mindful to make the disclosure of personal information optional and contextually appropriate for all attendees.

INDIGENOUS LAND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

A statement given at the beginning of an event/session/presentation to acknowledge the history of the land where the host or presenter resides.

Further reading: [A guide to indigenous land acknowledgment](#)

INTERPRETER

Someone who offers translation services in real time. For example, a visible sign-language interpreter or a virtual interpreter providing subtitling services.

LIVESTREAMING

The filming and live broadcast of an event on the internet for free or via a paid platform. Viewers of the online broadcast can listen and watch, and may be able to participate by sending written messages. Some platforms have built-in livestreaming capabilities (e.g., you can broadcast your Zoom event via YouTube).

LOGISTICS DOCUMENT

A document shared with attendees before the event containing clear instructions about how to participate. This may include a code of conduct/community participation guidelines, instructions for what to do if you have a question, orientation details for the venue or platform, the event hashtag, and any other important information. For virtual events, include easy-to-find links to key platforms or meeting rooms at the top of the document.

AKA: The “know-before-you-go” summary

MAKING A PACT FRAMEWORK

[CSCCE’s four-part PACT framework](#) outlines the key elements to consider when planning a virtual meeting or event: **P** for purpose, **A** for attendees, **C** for community management, and **T** for tech tools.

As each meeting or event is highly context-specific, the framework is intended to help you examine that context and then design an event that works for the attendees. What works in one context, such as using a specific online tool, may not work for participants who are unfamiliar with the technology. The power of making a PACT is in being intentional about meeting design for each event.

MODERATOR

The person, or people, responsible for ensuring your event meets its goals. A session moderator will guide the conversation, keep presenters to time, and handle questions from the audience. A technical moderator will ensure the projector functions and/or the virtual event platform is working, as well as monitoring any interactions with the virtual tools and addressing emergent needs such as technical questions.

AKA: Host, Session chair

See also: Facilitator, Technical facilitator, Event producer

OFFICE HOURS

These are supplementary events in addition to the main event. There can be pre-event office hours for discussing and answering questions, and post-event office hours for participants to ask additional questions and follow-up on their work.

ORGANIZING COMMITTEE

The organizing committee coordinates the logistics of the event such as running/hosting sessions, setting up infrastructure, and promoting the event.

See also: Steering committee

PAIR PROGRAMMING

Connecting each event attendee to another person at an event so that they might work together in some way. This is typically done prior to the event, so folks have a chance to connect with their partner. This provides peer support for first-time event participants, and may reduce attrition in technical workshops where troubleshooting support can be helpful.

AKA: Peer mentorship, Accountability buddies

POLLING

Using a set of questions to quickly engage participants at an event to assess understanding, aid decision making, and gather feedback. Can be done using the platform chat or by using tools like [Zoom Polls](#), [Slido](#), and [Mentimeter](#).

PRESENTER GUIDELINES

Guidelines that outline your expectations of presenters as a convener. This might include accessibility requirements (and a slide template), presentation length and Q&A format, and any preferred branding such as the event or sponsor logos.

PRE-WORK

Reading or other preparatory work to be completed by participants before joining the event.

Example: [Data Umbrella pre-work checklist](#)

REGISTRATION FORM

A mechanism for attendees to indicate that they would like to attend an event. Registration forms are often used for in-person and hybrid events as well as for virtual events. When used for virtual and hybrid events, they may be platform-dependent, and they may include questions about virtual accommodations, photo/video consent, etc. It's important to consider if an attendee's registration will tie directly (or not) to their access to a digital platform and, if so, how. For example, will the attendee have to use the same email to register and to access the platform? Will the email used for registration serve as the user ID for the platform? Will attendees need to sign up for the platform separately?

RESPONSE TIME

Otherwise known as, the "awkward pause" that facilitators leave after asking a question. For in-person events, the typical pause is "counting to 7" and in virtual events that goes a bit further: count to 10 (yes, really!).

RETROSPECTIVE / RECAP BLOG

This is an article or blog post that recounts key details about the events, shares new or existing resources, and synthesizes key learning.

Example: [CSCCE community call recap blog posts](#)

RISK ASSESSMENT

Part of your planning process should include identifying ways that things can go wrong. Rank your identified risks by their likelihood and impact. The likelihood refers to the probability of risks actually happening, while impact is the consequences if a potential risk happens.

See also: Risk mitigation

RISK MITIGATION

Once you've identified all of the things that could go wrong at your event (e.g., an internet outage or a piece of software requires an upgrade), decide if you can prevent something from happening (e.g., updating everything before the event starts) or put in place a plan for how you will handle an incident (e.g., drafting an email for participants that explains something has going wrong and creating a group or listserv that you can easily send the message to).

See also: Risk assessment

RUN-OF-SHOW

A single logistics document for event staff with the full agenda and added reminders or notes. For shorter events, this may be synonymous with an agenda, but for longer events, it can be really useful have a single place you know to check to find out what is coming up next.

SATELLITE EVENTS

Events that take place around the region/country/world that are connected to a "main event." All events could happen at the same time, or at different times leading up to or after the "main" event, and may be virtual or in-person.

See also: Watch party

SENSE-MAKING

A critical pause needed between presentations or topics for attendees to integrate concepts or reflect on how they apply to their own work or what they care about. The pause does not have to be long, even a couple of minutes will do, and can be structured (using reflective prompts) or unstructured.

SESSIONS

Blocks of time allocated to different themes, topics, or deliverables at your event. Participants can choose sessions of most interest to them, and an individual session or set of sessions can be repeated to accommodate multiple time zones. Sessions also allow you to easily switch formats, e.g., having a plenary lecture in session 1, concurrent workshops in session 2, and a panel discussion in session 3.

SILENT DOC'ING

Time set aside during an event for participants to write in the virtual notes document or other work product. This might involve responding to reflection prompts, crowd-sourcing resources, or answering icebreaker questions.

SOCIAL MEDIA CARD

This is usually a .jpg or .pdf file that uses graphics and text to display key details about an event. Social media cards are optimized to a platform (and it's a good idea to check the format requirements before creating a card as they do change over time) and help draw attention to your event by being visually appealing and easily shareable.

Things to include on your card:

- Date and time of the event
- Speaker names and affiliations
- Host organization branding
- Sponsor branding
- Event hashtag

STEERING COMMITTEE

A committee convened to help steer the direction of the program and agenda, and recommend speakers, sponsors, and audiences to engage.

See also: Organizing committee

SUBTITLES

Subtitles appear on screen in real-time in order to translate a verbal presentation in one language into a written presentation in another language, and do not communicate non-speech sounds. This can increase the accessibility of your event to international audiences.

See also: Captions

SUPPLEMENTARY TOOLS

Tools in addition to the basic webinar software / wrapper that may be used to support interaction during the event, e.g., a virtual whiteboard, polls, or a spatial networking tool.

Further reading: [CSCCE guidebook for selecting and testing online tools](#)

See also: Wrapper, Polling

SYNCHRONOUS CONTENT

At virtual or hybrid events, synchronous programming takes place live and everyone has to participate at the same time. Synchronous content types include plenary lectures, panel discussions, and social events. Synchronous content is generally less accessible, but does offer advantages for

building connection through a shared experience.

See also: Asynchronous content

TECHNICAL FACILITATOR

The person (or team) who assists with all of the technical aspects of an event. They are usually responsible for monitoring the waiting room and the chat, and for assisting presenters with screensharing and other setup. They are also key in planning, risk assessment, and troubleshooting processes.

See also: Moderator, Facilitator, Event producer

THEMES AND TRACKS

Some events have an overarching event theme around which participants are invited to submit session suggestions and other content such as posters or papers. An event may additionally be split into tracks with sessions that are unique to each track. Each track might focus on a sub-theme or on different levels of experience.

TRANSCRIPT

A written record of everything that was said at your event, and usually an option when activating a captioning tool. As with captioning, AI-based tools can do this increasingly well. However, consider how the presence of a verbatim transcript can affect participants' comfort with speaking freely and whether you will restrict downloading or copying the transcript.

TWITTER MOMENT

A virtual book/list of all the Tweets sent using the event hashtag. This can be embedded onto your website alongside other materials to show the engagement from attendees and those following along online.

Further reading: [How to create a Moment](#)

See also: Hashtag

VIRTUAL EVENTS PLATFORM

A software tool that is designed specifically to enable users to participate in a virtual event. May be browser-based and/or have an app. Virtual events platforms usually incorporate core functionality such as:

- Video conferencing – for plenary and concurrent sessions

- Text-based chat – public and direct message
- Agenda/session listings
- Directory of participants

Additional functionality, such as icebreakers and social networking may be included and varies between platforms.

Examples: [Gather](#), [Bevy](#), and [vFairs](#)

See also: Wrapper

VIRTUAL HELP DESK

The virtual equivalent of an event help desk; a place where event participants can find help with technical issues or questions they may have about the event’s agenda. Depending on your event and the technology available to you, this might be a shared inbox, a dedicated Slack channel, or a function of your event platform. The person or people staffing the help desk may require training to be effective at dealing with a variety of inquiries from participants.

VIRTUAL NOTES DOC(UMENT)

A shared Google doc, [Etherpad](#), or similar document in which event participants can take notes, ask questions, or participate in scaffolded activities. Virtual notes docs may also serve as minutes for your event.

See also: Archiving of artifacts, Silent doc’ing

WATCH PARTY

An in-person gathering where participants meet at a local venue to connect to a virtual or hybrid event. Such gatherings might be an official part of the event, or ad hoc happenings convened by participants.

See also: Satellite events

WEBINAR

A lecture or panel-based instructional event held virtually, where the primary goal is to convey information to participants.

WORKSHOP

An interactive event that incorporates activities, worksheets, or other supporting technology to guide participants through a process or to create a final product.

WRAPPER

An event platform that curates multiple others into a single “home” for your event. For example, if you are using Zoom for video conferencing, Google docs for shared notes, and SpatialChat for networking, a wrapper will give you a single domain from which participants can access all of these services, helping with navigation and discoverability.

Example: [Qigochat](#)

ZOOM BOMBING

Zoom bombing is when a bad actor joins your meeting and disrupts the proceedings in some way. Preventative measures such as a waiting room, passcode, or requiring participants to log into their Zoom account to join the event can help to prevent Zoom bombers from interrupting your meeting. Create a contingency plan for what you will do in the event of a Zoom bomber, such as creating backup shared notes docs and Zoom meeting links.

Further reading: [CSCCE Tech Tip Sheet - Zoom bombing: How to deal with bad actors during Zoom events](#)

ZOOM FATIGUE

The all-too-familiar feeling of not wanting to join yet another virtual event. This phenomenon has become more prevalent since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic and the global shift to more virtual gatherings. Be considerate of Zoom fatigue in your participants by offering plenty of breaks, suggesting they turn of their cameras from time to time, or providing instructions on how to access the event from a mobile device so that they can go for a walk while still participating.

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